

APPENDICES

Table 1 Questionnaire Used in Research

Indicator	Questions	Likert Scale 1	Likert Scale 2	Likert Scale 3	Likert Scale 4	Likert Scale 5
Biometric Security						
KB1	I feel that the biometric system (fingerprint/face recognition) on BCA Mobile is difficult for other parties to fake.					
KB2	I am confident that BCA Mobile's biometric authentication feature ensures that the account can only be used by me as the legitimate owner.					
KB3	The use of biometric features increases my sense of security when accessing the BCA Mobile application.					
KB4	In my opinion, biometric features are more secure than just using a conventional Access Code or PIN.					
KB5	The biometric system in BCA Mobile works consistently and recognizes my identity without error (accurate).					
Ease of Use						
KP1	I can understand how to use BCA Mobile easily without requiring complicated technical learning.					
KP2	I feel free and easy to control interactions/navigation in the BCA Mobile application.					
KP3	In my opinion, the BCA Mobile interface is simple, attractive, and not confusing.					
KP4	The features on BCA Mobile are easy to access and responsive to my transaction needs.					
KP5	Using the BCA Mobile application saves me effort and energy in conducting banking transactions.					

Service Speed

- KL1 The time required for the BCA Mobile application to log in is relatively fast.
- KL2 I can complete the transaction process on BCA Mobile in a short time.
- KL3 The waiting time (loading time) when switching menus in the BCA Mobile application is relatively short.
- KL4 The BCA Mobile system provides fast (real-time) transaction success confirmation notifications.
- KL5 The BCA Mobile application responds to my commands/touches immediately without long delays.

Customer Satisfaction

- KN1 The current performance of the BCA Mobile application has met or even exceeded my expectations.
- KN2 I feel happy and satisfied while using the BCA Mobile application service.
- KN3 Overall, I had a positive experience using BCA Mobile.
- KN4 I am satisfied with the capabilities of BCA Mobile's features in completing my financial transaction needs completely.

Customer Trust

- TR1 I believe that the BCA Mobile application is safe to use for financial transactions.
- TR2 I believe that my personal data and transaction history are well protected by BCA Mobile.
- TR3 I believe that the BCA Mobile system is reliable whenever I need it.

TR4 I believe that Bank BCA has integrity and will be responsible if there is a problem with my transaction.

TR5 I feel very confident to continue using BCA Mobile as my main financial transaction tool.

Figure 1 Overview of Elements in PLS-SEM

Table 3 Types of Measurement Models Used in Research

Indicator	Types of Measurement Models	Reasons
	Biometric Security	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I feel that the biometric system (fingerprint/face recognition) on BCA Mobile is difficult for other parties to fake. [KB1] I am confident that BCA Mobile's biometric authentication feature ensures that the account can only be used by me as the legitimate owner. [KB2] The use of biometric features increases my sense of security when accessing the BCA Mobile application. [KB3] 	Reflective Measurement Model	Indicators such as "difficult to counterfeit," "increases sense of security," and "more secure than a PIN" are symptoms, manifestations, or reflections of the construct. If we decide to remove one of the indicators, such as the fifth point ("The biometric system works consistently without recognition errors"), the remaining four indicators remain very much intact to capture the concept of "Biometric Security."

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In my opinion, biometric features are more secure than just using a conventional Access Code or PIN. [KB4] • The biometric system in BCA Mobile works consistently and recognizes my identity without error (accurate). [KB5] 		
Ease of Use		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I can understand how to use BCA Mobile easily without requiring complicated technical learning. [KP1] • I feel free and easy to control interactions or navigation in the BCA Mobile application. [KP2] • In my opinion, the BCA Mobile interface is simple, attractive, and not confusing. [KP3] • The features on BCA Mobile are easy to access and responsive to my transaction needs. [KP4] • Using the BCA Mobile application saves me effort and energy in conducting banking transactions. [KP5] 	<p>Reflective Measurement Model</p>	<p>Indicators such as "The app is easy to understand," "Customers feel in control," and "Using the app saves effort" are a consequence or reflection of perceived ease. If, for example, we decided to remove the item "Customers feel they can easily control interactions," the four remaining indicators would still fully measure the concept of "Ease of Use." These indicators are complementary, not separate components.</p>
Service Speed		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The time required for the BCA Mobile application to log in is relatively fast. [KL1] • I can complete the transaction process on BCA Mobile in a short time. [KL2] • The waiting time (loading time) when switching menus in the BCA Mobile application is relatively short. [KL3] • The BCA Mobile system provides fast (real-time) transaction success confirmation notifications. [KL4] • The BCA Mobile application responds to my commands/touches immediately without long delays. [KL5] 	<p>Reflective Measurement Model</p>	<p>Indicators such as "fast login time," "short loading time," and "fast application response without lag" are a reflection of a truly fast system. If we decide to remove one of the indicators, such as "System provides fast transaction confirmation" item, the remaining four items would still be very much a reflection of how fast the application service is perceived by users.</p>
Customer Satisfaction		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The current performance of the BCA Mobile application has met or even exceeded my expectations. [KN1] 	<p>Reflective Measurement Model</p>	<p>Indicators such as "pleasure and satisfaction," "positive assessment," and "exceeded expectations" are all indicators of satisfaction itself. If we decide to remove one of the indicators, such as the fourth point ("Satisfaction with feature</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I feel happy and satisfied while using the BCA Mobile application service. {KN2} • Overall, I had a positive experience using BCA Mobile. [KN3] • I am satisfied with the capabilities of BCA Mobile's features in completing my financial transaction needs completely. [KN4] 	<p>capabilities..."), the remaining three points would be a very complete measure of customer satisfaction with the application.</p>
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Customer Trust		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I believe that the BCA Mobile application is safe to use for financial transactions. [TR1] • I believe that my personal data and transaction history are well protected by BCA Mobile. [TR2] • I believe that the BCA Mobile system is reliable whenever I need it. [TR3] • I believe that Bank BCA has integrity and will be responsible if there is a problem with my transaction. {TR4} • I feel very confident to continue using BCA Mobile as my main financial transaction tool. {TR5} 	<p>Reflective Measurement Model</p>	<p>Indicators such as "Believe that BCA Mobile is secure" or "Confidence in using BCA Mobile" are symptoms or reflections of trust itself. For example, if we remove the indicator "Believe that BCA Bank is responsible if a problem occurs," the remaining four indicators remain intact and can measure the concept of "Customer Trust."</p>

Figure 2 Depiction of Reflective Measurement Model and Formative Measurement Model

Figure 3 Steps to Handle Discriminant Validity Problems

Figure 4 Steps to Interpret PLSpredict Results

Figure 5 Steps to Interpret Cross-Validated Predictive Ability Test (CVPAT) Results

Table 9 Results of Fornell-Larcker Values

	Biometric Security	Ease of Use	Service Speed	Customer Satisfaction	Customer Trust
Biometric Security	0.735				
Ease of Use	0.664	0.750			
Service Speed	0.640	0.750	0.766		
Customer Satisfaction	0.579	0.735	0.794	0.784	
Customer Trust	0.700	0.717	0.716	0.739	0.755

Table 10 Fornell-Larcker Values of Biometric Security Constructs With Other Constructs

Compared With	Correlation Value	Result	Inference
Ease of Use	0.664	0.735 > 0.664	Accepted
Service Speed	0.640	0.735 > 0.640	Accepted
Customer Satisfaction	0.579	0.735 > 0.579	Accepted
Customer Trust	0.700	0.735 > 0.700	Accepted

Table 11 Fornell-Larcker Values of Ease of Use Constructs With Other Constructs

Compared With	Correlation Value	Result	Inference
Biometric Security	0.664	0.750 > 0.664	Accepted
Service Speed	0.750	0.750 > 0.750	Not Accepted
Customer Satisfaction	0.735	0.750 > 0.735	Accepted
Customer Trust	0.717	0.750 > 0.717	Accepted

Table 12 Fornell-Larcker Values of Service Speed Constructs With Other Constructs

Compared With	Correlation Value	Result	Inference
Biometric Security	0.640	0.766 > 0.640	Accepted
Ease of Use	0.750	0.766 > 0.750	Accepted
Customer Satisfaction	0.794	0.766 < 0.794	Not Accepted
Customer Trust	0.716	0.766 > 0.716	Accepted

Table 13 Fornell-Larcker Values of Customer Satisfaction Constructs With Other Constructs

Compared With	Correlation Value	Result	Inference
Biometric Security	0.579	0.784 > 0.579	Accepted
Ease of Use	0.735	0.784 > 0.735	Accepted
Service Speed	0.794	0.784 < 0.794	Not Accepted
Customer Trust	0.739	0.784 > 0.739	Accepted

Table 14 Fornell-Larcker Values of Customer Trust Constructs With Other Constructs

Compared With	Correlation Value	Result	Inference
Biometric Security	0.700	0.755 > 0.700	Accepted
Ease of Use	0.717	0.755 > 0.717	Accepted
Service Speed	0.716	0.755 > 0.716	Accepted
Customer Satisfaction	0.739	0.755 > 0.739	Accepted

Table 15 Results of Cross Loadings Values

Indicator	Biometric Security	Ease of Use	Service Speed	Customer Satisfaction	Customer Trust
KB1	0.689	0.434	0.456	0.384	0.447
KB2	0.714	0.553	0.498	0.462	0.609
KB3	0.771	0.520	0.478	0.454	0.525
KB4	0.728	0.437	0.416	0.381	0.444
KB5	0.770	0.475	0.492	0.430	0.516
KP1	0.556	0.780	0.601	0.593	0.550
KP2	0.510	0.752	0.530	0.494	0.551
KP3	0.420	0.711	0.532	0.562	0.473
KP4	0.526	0.757	0.562	0.554	0.589
KP5	0.470	0.747	0.584	0.548	0.519
KL1	0.423	0.505	0.747	0.525	0.511
KL2	0.503	0.682	0.808	0.668	0.610
KL3	0.420	0.517	0.743	0.562	0.468
KL4	0.544	0.546	0.757	0.630	0.566
KL5	0.546	0.603	0.775	0.639	0.572
KN1	0.463	0.484	0.587	0.758	0.553

KN2	0.529	0.651	0.671	0.800	0.594
KN3	0.449	0.623	0.626	0.809	0.618
KN4	0.367	0.534	0.601	0.767	0.551
TR1	0.574	0.557	0.576	0.603	0.801
TR2	0.535	0.485	0.521	0.518	0.747
TR3	0.528	0.563	0.542	0.508	0.724
TR4	0.501	0.545	0.529	0.579	0.761
TR5	0.502	0.555	0.533	0.580	0.740

Table 16 Cross Loadings Values of Customer Satisfaction Indicators with Service Speed Construct

Indicator	Own Cross Loadings Value	Cross Loadings Values to Service Speed	Difference
KN1	0.758	0.587	+0.171
KN2	0.800	0.671	+0.129
KN3	0.809	0.626	+0.183
KN4	0.767	0.601	+0.166

Table 17 Cross Loadings Values of Service Speed Indicators with Customer Satisfaction Construct

Indicator	Own Cross Loadings Value	Cross Loadings Values to Customer Satisfaction	Difference
KL1	0.747	0.525	+0.222
KL2	0.808	0.688	+0.120
KL3	0.743	0.562	+0.181
KL4	0.757	0.630	+0.127
KL5	0.775	0.639	+0.136

Table 18 Cross Loadings Values of Service Speed Indicators with Ease of Use Construct

Indicator	Own Cross Loadings Value	Cross Loadings Values to Ease of Use	Difference
KL1	0.747	0.505	+0.242
KL2	0.808	0.682	+0.126
KL3	0.743	0.517	+0.226
KL4	0.757	0.546	+0.211
KL5	0.775	0.603	+0.172

Table 22 Results of Cross Loadings Values after KN2 and KL2 Indicators Removed

Indicator	Biometric Security	Ease of Use	Service Speed	Customer Satisfaction	Customer Trust
KB1	0.690	0.434	0.448	0.357	0.447
KB2	0.711	0.552	0.473	0.401	0.609
KB3	0.773	0.521	0.478	0.432	0.525
KB4	0.728	0.436	0.407	0.348	0.445
KB5	0.769	0.475	0.499	0.392	0.516
KP1	0.556	0.782	0.563	0.559	0.551
KP2	0.509	0.748	0.485	0.426	0.551
KP3	0.420	0.715	0.518	0.554	0.473
KP4	0.526	0.756	0.535	0.504	0.589
KP5	0.470	0.746	0.535	0.502	0.519
KL1	0.423	0.505	0.765	0.519	0.511
KL3	0.420	0.518	0.767	0.527	0.468
KL4	0.544	0.546	0.765	0.585	0.566
KL5	0.546	0.603	0.798	0.617	0.572
KN1	0.463	0.485	0.596	0.798	0.553
KN3	0.449	0.624	0.612	0.836	0.618
KN4	0.367	0.534	0.560	0.791	0.551
TR1	0.574	0.558	0.559	0.586	0.802
TR2	0.534	0.485	0.492	0.476	0.745
TR3	0.528	0.562	0.534	0.500	0.726
TR4	0.501	0.545	0.502	0.561	0.761
TR5	0.501	0.554	0.505	0.556	0.739

Table 23 Cross Loadings Values of Service Speed Indicators with Customer Satisfaction Construct after KN2 and KL2 Indicators Removed

Indicator	Own Cross Loadings Value	Cross Loadings Values to Customer Satisfaction	Difference
KL1	0.765	0.519	+0.246
KL3	0.767	0.527	+0.240
KL4	0.765	0.585	+0.180
KL5	0.798	0.617	+0.181

Table 24 Cross Loadings Values of Customer Trust Indicators with Customer Satisfaction Construct after KN2 and KL2 Indicators Removed

Indicator	Own Cross Loadings Value	Cross Loadings Values to Customer Satisfaction	Difference
TR1	0.802	0.586	+0.216
TR2	0.745	0.476	+0.269
TR3	0.726	0.500	+0.226
TR4	0.761	0.561	+0.200
TR5	0.739	0.556	+0.183